

Average Plate: Manufacturing

In Germany, Samsung smartphones are the most popular, with a market share of 36%, closely followed by iPhones with a market share of 34%. [3-6].

181 km (2 blocks)

> 18 min (2 blocks)

1 km $\hat{=}$ 239 g CO₂eq [1]

1 min $\hat{=}$ 12 l Water [2]

1 min $\hat{=}$ Working hours under abusive and dangerous (life-threatening) conditions

New purchases currently dominate the smartphone market. However, the number of used smartphones sold has risen steadily in recent years [4-10].

181 km (3 blocks)

77 min (3 blocks)

> 18 min (3 blocks)

The average age of smartphones in Germany is around 18 months [11].

2 blocks

2 blocks

2 blocks

CO₂: 12 blocks

H₂O: 8 blocks

The average person in Germany uses their smartphone for 152 minutes per day [12].

2 blocks

2 blocks

working conditions: 8 blocks

On most devices, energy-saving mode switches on when the battery level falls below a certain level and switches off again automatically during charging, so it is on from time to time [13, 14].

2 blocks

Around 64% of Germans have resold a smartphone or taken it to a recycling center in the past [15].

1 block

1 block

1 block